

Prevalence of Drug Abuse among Student in the University of Benin, Nigeria

Mustafa-Shaibu, Maryam* and Igbinoba-Ojo Iyayamwan, Omorovbiye

Department of Sociology and Anthropology University of Benin, Benin City, Edo State.
Correspondence: maryam.mustafa-shaibu@uniben.edu

Abstract

Drug abuse continues to be a major social problem among University undergraduate's students, with physical and mental health complications. Despite the known risks that are associated with drugs abuse, students continue using these drugs. The study examines the prevalence of drug abuse amongst student in University of Benin ,It identify the factors that influence the consumption of drug abuse amongst the University of Benin students and to investigate the effects of drug abuse on student academic performance. The Differential Association Theory by Edwin Sutherland guided this study, whereas questionnaires were used to collect information from respondent. The sample sizes for the study were 200 respondents and were purposively selected. More so, the findings showed that majority of student's abuse drug due to peer influence, academic related problems and one of the major reasons for drug abuse among the students was to be appreciated by friends and alcohol was said to be the most frequently abused drug followed by marijuana and cigarette. Addition to that, the rate of school or class attendance for students who involved in consumption of drugs was observed to be poor hence lead to low in academic performance.

Keywords: Prevalence, Drug Abuse, Harmful substances, Consumption,

Introduction

Today, more Nigerian youths are becoming drug dependants, while Nigeria gradually transits from the status of a drug-consuming nation to that of a drug-producing one (James and Omoregba, 2013). Young ones who are mainly from well-to-do homes are increasingly identifying with the 'big boys' that practice the use of substance like heroin and cocaine. Others substances like Indian hemp, which is frequently produced in Nigeria and other substances like Methamphetamine and tablet with codeine capable of intoxicating are mostly found in schools (Staff, 2012).

The youths in Nigeria like many other countries of the world are developing addiction to psychoactive substances. The abuse of hard drugs by students in Nigerian tertiary institutions has become an embarrassing occurrence to parents, schools authorities, government and the society at large (Muritala, Godwin, Anyio, Muhammad, and Ajiboye, 2015).

In a study by Fareo (2012), examined drug abuse among Nigerian adolescents; strategies for counselling and concluded that drug abuse is a problem that is causing serious concern to both individuals and government all over the world. She posited that the problem is prevalent among adolescents who in most cases are ignorant about the dangers inherent in drug abuse. Many of them engaged in drug abuse out of frustration, poverty, lack of parental supervision, peer influence and pleasure. However, she suggested that with effective counselling programme, the problems can be tackled.

In 2012, the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA) collected drugs use and abuse data from schools, records of patients admitted at mental health institutions for drug related problems and interview of persons arrested for drug offences. The result showed that youths constitute the high risk group for drug trafficking and abuse. Friends and school mates account for about 90% of the source of influence of the use and abuse of various psychoactive substances. In Nigeria, alcohol and cigarette are legal but these substances have also said to be “gateway drugs” to other more potent drugs like heroin and cocaine.

Drug abuse has been said to be any use of drugs for non-medical purposes almost always for altering consciousness. Drug abuse denotes substances that change the mental or physical state of a person and that may be used repeatedly for that effect leading to abnormality (Matowo, 2013). Drug and substance abuse has continued to ruin youth and subsequently education

despite various measures taken to stop it (Njeri and Ngesu, 2014). The consequences of any form of drug taking involve an interrelationship between the individual and his or her personality which may increase or decrease the vulnerability to drug abuse, and the characteristics of the drug consumed (Matowo, 2013). The health of young people is a key factor in the promotion and preservation of the health of the population as a whole because it determines the overall level of population health in the short term (Tsvetkova and Antonova, 2013). According to Oshodi, Aina, and Onajole (2010), majority of the Nigerian adolescents ignorantly or deliberately depend on one form of drug or the other such as tobacco, Alcohol, Cocaine, Heroin, Indian Hemp, Cannabis, Opium, Kola Nuts, Coffee, Aspirin, Codeine, Panadol, Paracetamol, Morphine, Ephedrine, Madras, Caffeine, Glue, Barbiturates, And Amphetamines for their various daily activities (social, educational, political moral and others).

According to Ajibulu (2011), the various effects of drug addiction or drug abuse are so devastating and very shameful to the extent that both the nation and international organizations all over the world are also worried about the spread of this scourge among the youths and adolescents and some of these consequences includes: Mental disorder, drop out from school, cultism, social violence, internet frauds, gang formation, destructions of normal academic activities, armed robbery, 419 syndrome, social miscreants (area boys and girls) lawlessness among youths, lack of respect for elders, rape, instant death and wasting of precious and innocent lives and loss of senses. (Ajibulu, 2011).

Universities students are the most susceptible to drug use amongst different youth groups in Nigeria because most of them live outside the watch of their parents or guardian. Uchendu and Ukonu (2016) stated that, it is evident that drug and substance abuse is still a problem in our tertiary institutions despite various measures taken to stop it.

The trend in drug abuse studies shows that prevalence of drug abuse is a manifestation that it is a social problem across nations in the world. It involves the improper use of drugs. It is an issue better solved within the socio-psychological and cultural domains. Therefore Drug abuse should be looked at in an environment where moral and standard are cultured. The abuse of drugs in turn has created numerous social vices in the society which formed the backdrop of this study conceived to assess the prevalence of drug abuse amongst student in the University of Benin and suggest measures to curtail the menace in Benin City.

Research Questions.

To guide this study, the following research questions are posed.

1. What is the prevalence rate of drug abuse amongst the University of Benin students?
2. What are the factors that influence the consumption of these drugs amongst the University of Benin students?
3. What are the effects of drug abuse on student academic performance in the University of Benin?

Objectives of the study

1. Assess the prevalence of drug abuse amongst university of Benin students.
2. Identify the factors that influence the consumption of drug abuse amongst the University of Benin students
3. To find out the effects of drug abuse on students' academic performance in the University of Benin

The Concept of Drug Abuse

Drug abuse may be defined as the “arbitrary” over dependence or miss-use of one particular drug with or without a prior medical diagnosis from qualified health practitioners. (Oluremi,

2012). Drug Abuse is the harmful use of mind altering drugs. It added that the term usually refers to problem with illegal drugs, which also include harmful use of legal prescription drugs, Such as in self-medication.

Drugs are psychoactive chemical materials that affect the central nerve system until a user is in a condition of intoxication, addiction, and behavioural problems. Drugs are chemical materials dangerous to individuals that partake in them, as it changed how the mind and body function. Drugs are a special term referring to substances that harms a user's physical, mental, and emotional health as well as behaviour after use. As a result, a drug abuser becomes addicted and is highly dependent on the substance. Continued drug abuse leads to damage to self, family, society, and country (Razali, & Madon,(2016).

Drug abuse not only covers the mode of action or function of the drug, but also refers to functional disorder and maladaptation due to misuse of the substances (Fletcher, 2010). The brain is the main organ that controls the entire function of the body, emotions, and normal behaviour of the individual. Drugs and alcohol could disrupt the original function of the brain and caused interruption in conversation and work performance and leads to destruction behaviour (Bonell, Sorhaindo, Allen, Strange, Wiggins, and Fletcher, 2010). Functional disorder is affected by chemical substances and its effects are reflected in the drugs consumed. The personality of drug addicts plays a role in determining if they had misused drugs.

Drug Abuse in Nigeria

Horrible youthful activities are widespread in Nigeria to the extent that they have been giving a lot of concern to the society, government and other stake holders in Nigeria. In primary schools, peers engage in organized crimes and disrupt normal academic programs. In secondary schools and most Nigerian universities, the activities of secret cults are known to have been

source of threat to lives and property. Outside the campuses, a lot of ritual killings are taking place. (Abudu, Oshodi, Aina, & Onajole, 2010). The impact of drug abuse among Nigerian adolescents has been a feature of a morally bankrupt, corrupt and wasted generation and loss of our societal values and ideals. The situation now appears to be such that no one can argue ignorance of what is happening (Abudu, 2010). We cannot sit and illegitimately pretend on the menace of drug abuse among our adolescents.

According to Giade, (2011), any nation being used by drug barons as a transit route has the potentials of becoming a drugs abuse consumer's country, drugs abuse threaten the security of every nation, tearing apart our societies, spawning crime, spreading diseases such as aids, and killing our youths and our future".

The Government of Nigeria seems to lose sight of its responsibilities, though it claims that tobacco should be regulated in a market oriented frame work, which strikes an optimal balance and the need to ensure healthy work force. The fear is that adolescents are lured into early death from Cardio Vascular diseases (CVD), lung cancer and other tobacco related diseases. (Abudu, 2010; Giade, 2011). Already, Nigerian adolescents are being offered cigarettes through promotions and musical concerts. Some teens will experiment and stop, or continue to use occasionally without significant problems. While others will develop addiction, moving on to more dangerous and hard drugs and causing considerable harm to themselves and the society at large. Despite the effort of many concerned individuals and organizations to curb this menace, many individuals still present these drugs as though they are harmless. They give them slogans such as "for greatness" "for brighter life" (Oshodi, Aina & Onajole, 2010).

Drug and Substance Abuse from a Global Perspective

According to American Addiction Centre in 2020 and National Institute on Drugs Abuse in 2018, the more often drugs are used, the more they will impact brain chemicals and circuitry which can lead to drug dependence and withdrawal symptoms when the drugs process out of the body. Drugs are a special term referring to substances that harms a user's physical, mental, and emotional health as well as behaviour after use. As a result, a drug abuser becomes addicted and is highly dependent on the substance. Continued drug abuse leads to damage to self, family, society, and country (Galea, Nandi, & Viahov, 2010). Drug abuse not only covers the mode of action or function of the drug, but also refers to functional disorder and maladaptation due to misuse of the substances. The brain is the main organ that controls the entire function of the body, emotions, and normal behaviour of the individual. The factors contributing to youth substance abuse have been identified and promulgated by the electronic and print media worldwide. These factors have been further authenticated by research (Hong Kong Narcotic Division, 2010). Ali (2010); Bamberg (2008); Community Anti-Drug Coalitions of America, U.S. (2008). Bradford, Burns, Vaughn, and Barber, (2008). Some of which are dysfunction families due to unstable low income, poor marital relationship, conflicts, divorce, separation, single parenthood, long working hours of family members, limited family time, ineffective communication, easy access to drugs within immediate neighbourhood, failure of school achievement, feeling boredom, undesirable peer influence, intergenerational addiction and negative peers.

The World Health Organization (WHO) report noted that alcohol abuse results in 3million deaths annually across the world, Nigeria inclusive; this represents 5.3 % of all deaths (WHO, 2018). Apart from cannabis misuse, there is a growing abuse of synthetic drugs, which were once strange to the Nigerian society. Amphetamine, methamphetamine, cocaine, heroin,

paint thinner, glue, cough syrup made with codeine, cement and animal excreta are being widely abused. According to Punch Newspaper in 2016, between 2010 and 2012, six methamphetamine factories were discovered in Delta and Lagos states, said the National Drug Law Enforcement Agency (NDLEA).

The development of medicinal Chemistry resulted in several synthetic compounds such as Barbiturates, Benzodiazepines and Amphetamines. These were originally proposed for use as therapeutic compounds for restoration of health. Later the compounds were refined to more potent compounds and faster routes of administration were devised which favour most rapid transport of central nervous system contributing to abuse. The attitude of society and pattern of use of psychoactive substances have changed over time. The global context in the use of drugs indicates the erosion of traditional theoretical boundaries which also affect the beliefs, value systems and perceptions towards use of drugs (Gakuru, 2012).

According to United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) in 2010, the World Health Organization has estimated that more than 225 million individuals or one in every twenty adults have consumed an illegal drug once in the year 2010. In addition, World Health Organization (WHO) in 2014 reported that more than fifteen million persons are indulged in drug abuse and the problem of injectable drug abuse has been reported in more than 145 nations.

Common drugs abused by university students

The Federal Bureau of Investigation and U.S. Drug Eradication Agency (2010), has identify some of the known and most commonly drugs abused by students, which includes; heroin, marijuana, methamphetamine and hallucinogens. Reports from all over the world about

this menace of drug abuse are severe. Amphetamines are used among students, (Oshodi, Aina & Onajole, 2010).

The most common drugs been abused by university undergraduates from recent related literature includes the following; Alcohol, Cannabis (Marijuana), Heroin, Cocaine, Tobacco.

Alcohol

This is a natural product of the fermentation of sugar and water. Alcohol is the drug present in beer, liquor, wine, palm wine, Ogogoro, brandy, whisky, gin, rum and so on. Alcohol interferes with reasoning and the ability to control oneself. Long-term use affects the liver and brain (Odelola, 2008). The use of alcohol has been observed to be associated with adverse health and social consequences arising from its intoxicating ability to its toxic and dependence producing properties. Alcohol was discovered to contribute to traumatic outcome that sometimes kill or disable the user at a relatively young age, thereby resulting into loss of many years of life to death or disability, (Chikere & Mayowa, 2011).

Tobacco

Nicotine is the drug present in the tobacco leaf. Tobacco is an unrestricted drug that can be found in public places, such as motor parks and marketplaces. The brands of cigarette available in Nigeria today include Benson and Hedges, Gold Leaf, Consulate, Rothmans, London, Sweet Menthol, and Gold Bond. (Odelola, 2008).

Cannabis (Marijuana)

Cannabis is commonly known as marijuana in Nigeria. It is the drug that is largely used by university undergraduates, and it is also the most controversial of all the popular drugs used by undergraduate students. Marijuana is derived from the dried leaves of flowers of hemp

plants and used in form of cigarette as narcotic or hallucinogen and also farms where marijuana is cultivated is scattered all over Nigeria, (Abudu, 2008).

The herbal form of marijuana is the most abused drug in West Africa, because it is likely cultivated all over the region and it is therefore affordable, marijuana appears to be the most commonly abused drug students, (UNODC, 2011). In the same vein, Hales (2007) asserted that drug use on universities campus in America is on the increase with almost half of the undergraduates attesting to the fact that they use marijuana.

Heroin

Another form of drug that is commonly abused by undergraduates is called "heroin" According to Kinch (2013), heroin is derived from the grooming substance extracted from the opium poppy and it is powdery in form. Opium is prepared by boiling the gum opium and successfully filtering out the impurity. Depending on the process, opium can be produced as a paste, powder or solution. It is known by different names such as horse, junk, smack, stuff, etc.

Cocaine

According to National Institute on Drug Abuse (2013), cocaine is a powdery addictive stimulant drug made from leaves of the cocoa plants, native to South America. It is one of the most addictive drugs and produces short-term euphoria energy and talkativeness in addiction to potentially dangerous physical effects like heart rate and blood pressure.

In summary, the types of drugs commonly abused by university undergraduates differs in terms of availability and economic effect, that is, how accessible some certain drugs are, and the cost involved in acquiring some hard drugs.

Causes of Drug Abuse

Studies have revealed that most of the drug addicts started smoking from their youths. As they grow older they seek new thrills and gradually go into hard drug abuse, (Oshodi, Aina and Onajole, 2010). A nationwide survey of high school students reported that 65 per cent used drugs to have good time with their friends 54 per cent wanted to experiment to see what it is like, 20 per cent to 40 per cent used it to alter their moods, to feel good, to relax, to relieve tension and to overcome boredom and problems (Abudu, 2008).

No single factor could be defined as solely responsible for the abuse of drugs but the following are some of the causes of young people vulnerable to drug abuse in Nigeria. (Oshodi, Aina, & Onajole, 2010; Igwe, 2009; Abudu, 2008; Oluremi, 2012; Desalu., 2010; Ajibulu, 2011; Henry and Smith 2010).

2.7 Consequence of Drug Abuse.

Over the past two decades, the use of illegal drugs and misuse of therapeutic drugs have spread at an unprecedented rate and have penetrated every part of the globe. No nation has been spared from the devastating problem caused by drug abuse. (Njeru & Lewis, 2014). It has been observed from studies that substance abuse may impair cognitive development which in turn reduces academic achievement and disrupts academic progression. Studies have associated poor academic performance, students missing classes, difficulty in keeping up with academic responsibility, failing tests, dropping out of school due to poor grades with Alcohol.

Nonetheless, Attah, Baba and Audu (2016), stated that drug abuse/addiction has gone a long way to create several health and social problems and dangers globally. Such problems include mental illness, cancer of the lungs, school drop-outs, suicide and juvenile delinquency. Tertiary institutions in Nigeria are not an exception as previous studies have identified high consumption of drugs on campus; In view of the well-documented cases on the prevalence and

cause of drug abuse in tertiary institutions and secondary schools, it is necessary to investigate the impact that drug abuse has on the academic performance of students in tertiary institutions. Drugs affect a student's concentration and thus interest in school and extracurricular activities, which results to increased absenteeism and drop outs (Emmanuel, Valentine, Terna, Habu, Chia, & Achukwu, 2017).

In addition, Akanbi (2014), stated that student who abuse drugs spends more money on the purchase of illegal drugs at the detriment of purchasing their academic books. Similarly, a study conducted by Uchendu and Ukonu (2016), revealed that drug abuse among students is tantamount to poor performance as the objectives of education to students are over run by aggressive behaviour, violence and withdrawal. It becomes impossible for such students to concentrate on studies or even interact with fellow students or teachers

According to the study alcohol can have a secondary effect on academic performance of students whose peers drink by: taking care of a drunken friend and colleague who ordinarily may not be in a right frame at that state of being drunk and these caretakers possibly may become victim of assault by the drunken friend or colleague. (Uchendu and Ukonu, 2016).

According to Kamlesh and Soma (2012), Drug Abuse has effects in the following ways in the life of individuals in the society.

1.2 Theoretical Framework: The Differential Association Theory

The differential association theory emerged within the lessons of the eminent criminologist Edwin H. Sutherland (1883-1950). It is one of those criminological theories explaining criminal behavior through the process of socialization and the contacts between members of social groups to which one belongs a certain delinquent. Sutherland presented his theory of differential association in 1939 in his work named *Principles of Criminology* (Botterweck, 2011).

The theory of differential association is one of the most important criminological theories in the last sixty years. According to this theory, an individual learns delinquent behavior, accepts it from others, and learning flows through the communication process. An individual becomes delinquent, if he accepts values that support the violation of law, and not the values of conventional culture. Edwin Sutherland formulated Differential Association Theory (1939), to explain criminal and all other forms of deviant behavior including drug abuse. According to Sutherland's differential association, argued that deviant and criminal behavior is learned like any other behavior, through the act of communication and interaction between groups and significant others. In other words, university undergraduates learn how to use drugs due to the type of friends they associate with. More so, when an individual significant others engage in deviant behavior or behavior of a drug addict, such behavior will be learned as a result of exposure.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design in examining the prevalence of drug abuse amongst student in the University of Benin Benin City. The study adopted a quant-qual method of data collection. The scope and population size was restricted to university of Benin students as at 2018/2019 academic session .The target population is 39,243 as obtained from the academic planning of the University of Benin.

Using the simple random sampling technique, five departments were selected. They were Economics and Statistics, Political Science, Social Work, Sociology and Anthropology and Geography. Using the purposive sampling technique, the researcher purposively selected a sample size of 200 respondents from the five departments. Department of Economics and Statistics contributed a sample size of 40 respondents, Department of Political Science

contributed a sample size of 40 respondents, Department of Social Work contributed a sample size of 40 respondents, and Department of Sociology and Anthropology contributed a sample size of 40 respondents and Department of Geography also contributed 40. Therefore, the sample sizes for the study were 200 respondents. Questionnaire will be used as an instrument for collecting data from both male and female undergraduate students of University of Benin. The data collected was analysed using simple statistics. The questionnaires were checked for completeness, accuracy of information and uniformity. The questionnaires were checked to see if there were errors and omissions, adequate information and legibility and relevant responses.

Results of Findings

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Age of Respondents

AGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
15 – 20 years	33	17.36
21 – 25 years	75	39.47
26 - 30 years	38	20.00
31 and above years	44	23.15
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 1 above shows that 33 respondents representing 17.36% were 15-20 years, 75 respondents representing 39.47% were 21-25 years, 38 respondents representing 20% were 26-30 years, while 44 respondents representing 23.15% were 31 and above years.

Table 2: Sex of Respondents

SEX	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Male	75	39.47
Female	115	60.52
TOTAL	190	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 2 Shows that (39.47%, which translated to 75 respondents) were male, while (115 respondents which translate to 60.52%) were female. This indicates that the female were more represented than males.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Religion

Religion	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Christianity	107	56.3
Islam	57	30
African traditional Religion	16	8.42
Others	10	5.26
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 3 above shows that 107 respondents representing 56.3% were Christian, 57 respondents representing 30% were Muslim, 16 respondents representing 8.42% were African Traditional Religion, while 10 respondents representing 5.26% were other religion This implies that all the respondents belong to one religion or the other.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by Department

DEPARTMENT	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Economics and Statistics	40	21.05
Political Science	50	26.32
Social Work	25	13.15
Sociology and Anthropology	60	31.58
Geography	15	7.89
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

Table 4 Shows that (21.05%, which translated to 40 respondents) were from Economic and Statistics (26.32%, which translated to 50 respondents) were from Political Sciences, (13.15%, which translated to 25 respondents) were from Social Work, (31.58. %,

which translated to 60 respondents) were from Sociology and Anthropology, (7.89%, which translated to 15 respondents) were from Geography.

Table 5: Prevalence of Drug Abuse

Have you ever used drugs?

Table 4.7: Understanding the meaning of drug abuse?

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	147	77.36
No	43	22.63
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 5 above, it was observed that 147 respondent represent 77.36 agree that they have used drugs, while 43 represent 22.63 disagreed to using of drugs. Similarly, the following are the responses which are gotten from respondent who agreed that they understand the meaning of drug abuse.

It is the use of drugs against doctor’s prescription or an overdose of it even when prescribed. Drug abuse is the use of a particular drug excessively. Drug abuse is when an individual or group of individuals voluntarily take drugs without the consent of a doctor, or if prescribed by the doctor, they take an overdose of it. Drug abuse means taking overdose of a drug that wasn’t prescribed by the doctor. Drug abuse means taking drugs against instructions from doctors. Firstly, drug abuse is any substance that causes a change in an organism physiology or psychology when consumed. Drug abuse is the use of a drug in an excessive amount or the abuse of prescription. Drug abuse is the illegal use of drug

without following the instructions of qualified medical personnel.

Drug abuse is the taking of a substance outside the recommendation of the medical doctors. 08/07/2021, Fieldwork

2021.

Table 6: Have you use drugs other than those required for medical reasons?

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	76	40
No	114	60
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The table shows that 76 respondents representing 40% agree that they have used drugs other than those required for medical reasons, while 114 respondents representing 60% do not agree to it.

Table 7. Is drug abuse associated with undergraduate student only?

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	71	35.78
No	119	62.22
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The table shows that 68 respondents representing 37.78% agree that drug abuse is associated with undergraduate student only while 112 respondents representing 62.22% do not agree.

SECTION C: TYPE OF DRUG COMMONLY ABUSED BY STUDENT

Table 8. Drugs mostly abused by students?

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Alcohol	70	36.84
Marijuana	56	29.47
Cigarette	54	28.42
Tobacco	10	5.26
Heroin	-	-
Others	-	-
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The table shows that 70 respondents representing 36.84% were into alcohol, 56 respondents representing 29.47% were into marijuana, 54 respondents representing 28.42% were into Cigarette, while 10 respondents representing 5.26% were into Tobacco, no responses on Heroin and the various comments are as follows:

The use of different types of drugs among students is very common in off campus where there locations where this drugs are sold. University has become one of the most common places where different drugs such as Alcohol, Marijuana, Cigarette, Tobacco, Heroin are found, sold, and abused. For many students, who are admitted into University of Benin created opportunity for them to try so many things including drugs, to some these new experiences without the supervision of parents. Unfortunately, this includes engaging in risky behaviour without fear of the real consequences. To some students the rates of abuse of drugs in University of Benin campuses (i.e., Ekenwan and Ugbowo Campus) have more than tripled for some substances, leading to increased tolerance and possible addiction later on.

Majority of the University of Benin students’ responses revealed that students ignorantly depend on one form of drug or the other (such as Tobacco, Indian hemp, cocaine, morphine, Heroine, and Alcohol) for their various daily activities.

Similarly are highlighted in the transcript of interview responses, for instance

Because it is often prevalent among youth in the society as is often influenced by peer pressure. It is easier and cheaper to get. It is found in drinks (hard drinks). Because alcohol is present in most of the drink or wine that people drink.

08/07/2021, Fieldwork 2021.

It is very common in the society. To the students, they believe it help them forget their worries and help them to feel relax. Because they feel it makes them to be strong and harden. Because of the stress and pressure from school, they tend to take it to ease their selves from stress. They use it for different purpose. It is the popular one called “Igbo”. It has become the order of the day among youths. Because some student see others doing it. It is one of the most common and prevalent. Because of friends or just to know how it feel like, to feel high, peer group influence, anti – depressant. It makes them get high and give them fake sense of belonging. They don’t think it is harmful and feel they can easily access it .It is cheap to buy. It is sold in most shops and stores, availability and affordable.

08/07/2021, Fieldwork 2021.

The responses shows that some students take drugs to increase intelligence, while some students take drugs out of curiosity, Some University of Benin students abuse different types of drugs because they have a lot of pocket money. Responses from University of Benin students

shows that the availability of different drugs has lead to its abuse, and that this may be due to poor teachers/parental example and upbringing leading to use of different drugs such as alcohol, marijuana, cigarette, tobacco, and heroin. Responses also show that peer group/peer pressure is capable of influencing student into taking of these drugs and that many University of Benin students a take drugs out of frustration.

Table 9: How did undergraduate students in the University of Benin get these drugs?

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
From Friends	68	35.79
From Neighboring Street	102	53.68
Within School Environment	20	10.52
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The table shows that 68 respondents representing 35.79% got drugs from friends, 102 respondents representing 53.68% got drugs from Neighbouring Street, while 20 respondents representing 10.52% got drugs from the school environment.

Table 10: Drug seen abuse by people

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Alcohol	80	42.11
Marijuana	46	24.21
Cigarette	50	26.31
Tobacco	14	7.37
TOTAL	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

From the table, it is show that 80 respondent representing 42.11% seen people abusing Alcohol, while 46 respondent representing 24.21 % have seen people abusing Marijuana, while 50 respondents representing 26.31% seen people abusing Cigarette and 14 respondent representing 7.37% have seen people abusing Tobacco.

Table 11: What do you think is the effect of drug abuse among undergraduate students in the University of Benin

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Beneficial	69	36.32
Damaging	106	55.78
No effect	15	7.89
Total	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The table shows that 69 respondents representing 36.32% said that they think drug abuse is beneficial effect among undergraduate students in the University of Benin, 106 respondents representing 55.78% said that they think that drug abuse has damaging effect among undergraduate students in the University of Benin, while 15 respondents representing 7.89% said that they think drug abuse has no effect among undergraduate students in the University of Benin.

Table 4.12: Does abuse of drugs have any health complications among undergraduate students in the University of Benin?

RESPONSE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE %
Yes	150	78.95
No	14	7.37
May Be	20	10.53
I don't Know	6	3.16
Total	190	100

Source: Field survey, 2021

The table shows that 150 respondents representing 78.95% agree that abuse of drugs have health complications among undergraduate students in the University of Benin, 14 respondents representing 7.37% do not agree that abuse of drugs have any health complications among undergraduate students in the University of Benin, 20 respondents representing 10.53% said may be abuse of drugs may have health complications among undergraduate students in

the University of Benin, while 6 respondents representing 3.16% said they don't know if abuse of drugs have health complications among undergraduate students in the University of Benin.

Similarly, from the response highlighted in the transcripts of interviews, for instance respondent described the following as the health complications of drug abuse

Lungs problems in the long run, loss of memories, mental imbalance, it could lead to health complications that may lead to untimely death of a person, heart failure, seizure, heart problems and kidney problems. Damage kidney or Liver, lungs cancer, weakening the body, terminal disease, it distort the body system, death, it damages some sensitive organ in the body, it can cause brain damage, abnormal behaviour sometimes psychological abnormal disposition, financial problems, homelessness, criminal activity which can later lead to imprisonment, blood pressure, it can alter and cause harm to their body system, it could lead to destruction of vital organs in the body, it can damage the brain which can lead to madness, it can lead to addiction, loss of concentration, becoming aggressive, it cause distraction thereby making them to lose focus.

08/07/2021, Fieldwork 2021.

Health effects of drug abuse often depend on the specific drug or drugs used, how they are taken, how much is taken, the person's health, and other factors that may be contributed to such effect. Short-term effects can range from changes in appetite, wakefulness, heart rate, blood pressure, mood to heart attack, stroke, psychosis, overdose, and even death. These health effects may occur after just one use. On the other hand, longer-term effects can include heart or lung sickness, malignant growth, psychological sickness, hepatitis, and others. Long-term

drug abuse can likewise prompt dependence. Illicit drug use is a mind issue. Not every person who uses medications will get dependent, yet for a few, tranquilize use can change how certain mind circuit functions. These mind changes meddle with how individuals experience ordinary delights in life, for example, nourishment and sex, their capacity to control their feeling of anxiety, their dynamic, their capacity to learn and recall, and so forth. These progressions make it significantly harder for somebody to quit taking the drug in any event, when it is having negative effect on their life and they need to stop.

Additionally, students who abuse drug have indirect effect on both the individuals who are ingesting drugs or on people around them. This can incorporate influencing an individual's nourishment; rest; decision making and impulsivity; and hazard for injury, viciousness, injury, and transmittable diseases.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the findings of this study revealed that the respondent who are single are 166 respondent with 87.36%, married 24 respondent with 12.62 %, in age distribution, it was observed that students who fall into age category 21 – 25 has the highest respondent with 75 (39.47%) respondents followed by age category 31 and above which has 44 (23.15%), in sex distribution, it was observed that the female category has 115 (60.52 %) respondents and the males category has 75 (39.47%), in religion distribution, it was observed that the Christian religion has 107 (56.3% respondents, Islam has 57 (30%) respondent, African tradition has 16 (8.42%), in Department distribution, it was observed that Economics and Statistic has 40 (21.05%), Political science has 50 (26.32%) social Work has 25 (13.58%) Sociology and Anthropology has 60 (31.15%), Geography has 15 (7.89%), in resident distribution, respondents in school hostel has 53 (27.89%) off Campus has 137 (72.10%).

In accessing the prevalence of drug abuse, the result revealed that 147 respondent representing 77.36 % agreed that they understand the meaning of drug abuse while 43 respondent representing 22.63 % disagreed to understanding the meaning of drug abuse, in using drug other than those required for medical reasons, 76 respondent representing 40% agreed on using drug other than required for medical reason, while 114 respondents representing 60% said they have not used drugs other than required for medical reason, 71 (35.78%) said that drug abuse is associated with only undergraduate student, while 119 representing 62.22% said that drug abuse is not associated only with undergraduate student. The prevalence of drug abuse in the University of Benin exit. This finding collaborate with the study by United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) in 2010, the World Health Organization has estimated that more than 225 million individuals or one in every twenty adults have consumed an illegal drug once in the year 2010.

In examining how the drugs are gotten by the students who abuse them, 68 (35.79%) get the drugs from friends, 102 (53.68) get the drugs from neighbouring street, while 20 (10.52%) get the drugs within the school environment, the result shows that drugs abuse by people, has a high estimate of 80 (42.11%) and some response shows that people are seen to abuse alcohol, 46 (24.21%) and responses shows that people abuse marijuana. 50 (26.31%) shows that people abuse cigarette, while 14 (7.37%) revealed that people abuse tobacco. In examine the types of drugs that are commonly abused the result revealed that 70 (36.84%) of students abuse alcohol, 56 (29.47%) abuse marijuana, 54 (28.42%) abuse cigarette, while 10 (5.26%) abuse tobacco, this findings contradict the study by United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC, 2011) who found that the herbal form of marijuana is the most abused drug in West Africa, because it is likely cultivated all over the region and it is therefore affordable, marijuana appears to be the most commonly abused drug students.

In identifying factors are responsible for drug abuse among students, the result revealed that 97 (51.05 %) agreed, this shows that the peer group influences drug abuse. 48 (25.26%) disagreed that peer group can influence drug abuse. In identifying if inherit gens from parents can lead to student drug habit, the result shows that 79 (41,58 %) disagreed, 36 (18.95%) agreed, 45 (23.68%), other responses shows “maybe” while 30 (15.79%) were undecided. in identifying the reason why students engage in drug in university of Benin, 90 (47.37%) responses shows that students engage in drug abuse because of their academic problems. The result also shows that 36 (18.95%) responses are of the opinion that they took drug for Leisure. The result further shows that 14 (7.37%) responses gain power through drug abuse.

According to the findings, 90 (47.37%) of the students engage in drug abuse because of academic related problems, this agrees with the study by Emmanuel, Valentine, Terna, Habu, Chia, and Achukwu (2017) who found that drugs abuse affects student’s concentration and thus interest in school and extracurricular activities. This may also implicate increased absenteeism and drop outs. Also, the study also agreed with a study conducted by Uchendu and Ukonu (2016), which revealed that drug abuse among students is tantamount to poor performance as the objectives of education to students are over run by aggressive behaviour, violence and withdrawal.

In investigating into the effects of drug abuse on students’ academic performance in the University of Benin, the result shows that 69 (36.32%) of the students abuse drug in one way or the other due to the benefit that accrue from it. The result also shows that 106 (55.78%) agreed that drug abuse has damaging effect on student in the University of Benin. The result further revealed that 15 (7.89%) are of the opinion that drug abuse has no effect on students. In investigating the ways in which drug abuse affect students, the result indicate that 60 (31.58%) agreed that drug abuse affects students emotionally, the result also shows that 33

(17.37%) agreed drug abuse affect student physically, the result further affirm that 97 (47.89%) agreed that drug abuse affects student Psychologically. In investigating the health complication of drug abuse among undergraduate student in University of Benin, the result demonstrates that 150 (78.95 %) agreed that drug abuse has health complications on students, while 14 (7.37%) disagree that drug abuse has health implication on students. This finding agrees with the study by Attah, Baba and Audu (2016), who found that drug abuse/addiction has go a long way to create several health implications and social problems as well as dangers to serveral aspect of human endeavour such as deviant behaviour, insecurity etc. other biological implication of drug abuse includes mental illness, cancer of the lungs, school drop-outs, suicide and juvenile delinquency.

CONCLUSION

Drug abuse is a social problem basically associated with young people (not only undergraduate student) and it has a continue damage to self, family, society and country when it becomes a habit. These young people involve themselves in taking hard drugs and excessive taking of some drugs which may alter the body system or may cause damage to the health. Drug abuse is very common among undergraduates, they take drugs, to get high or to make them feel big or for them to just feel among or fit into the environment while some take this drugs through the influence of friends or other people around them.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study the following recommendations were made;

Preventive health education should be intensified in schools and media to raise students' awareness of risks of drug abuse. Media should be used to address drug abuse because of its great influence on the youths. Any education programme aimed at addressing drug abuse

among students should therefore be holistic and address both the risk and protective factors. The aim should be to strengthen the protective factors where potential buffers include strong family bonding, positive role models, school commitment and strong belief in one's own efficacy. Parents require information on how to be good role models and the right values by family members

Benefits of healthy lifestyle choices and development of skills needed in making informed and responsible decisions to resist drug abuse among students should be emphasized. The government should enforce laws to regulate the production and consumption of the local breweries which seem to be the bases where students learn the behaviour of alcohol abuse.

Bibliography

- Abdu-Raheem, B. O. (2013). Sociological factors to drug abuse and the effects on secondary school students' academic performance in Ekiti and Ondo States, Nigeria. *Contemporary Issues in Education Research – Second Quarter*.
- Akanbi, M.I., Godwin, A., Anyio, B.T, Muhammad, M., & Ajiboye, S.A. (2014), Impact of Substance Abuse on Academic Performance among Adolescent Students of Colleges of Education in Kwara State, Nigeria *Scholarly Journal of Education* Vol. 3(7), 75-79,
- Attah, A.P., Baba, E. & Audu, J.S. (2016), The Effects of Drug Abuse and Addiction on Academic Performance of Students in Federal Polytechnic Idah, Kogi State Nigeria, *International Journal of Democratic and Development Studies*, Vol. (2).
- Adegboro J. S. (2014). Drug abuse among students of Adekunle Ajasin University, AkungbaAkoko, Ondo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*.
- Adegboyega, L. O., Oniye, A. O. & Adigun, A. (2015). Motivations for drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Ife Journal of Behavioural Research*.
- Adegboyega, L. O., Yahaya, L A., Alwajud-Adewusi, M. B. & Aminu, H. P. (2016). Manifestation of depression among undergraduate students in Kwara State, Nigeria:

- Implications for counselling. *IIUM Journal of Educational Studies*, 4(2), 85-96. (A Journal of the Kulliyah of Education, International Islamic University, Malaysia).
- Adigun, A. A. (2014). *Prevalence of, and motivation for drug abuse among students of tertiary institutions in Kwara State*. Unpublished M.Ed Project, Department of Counsellor Education, University of Ilorin, Ilorin, Nigeria.
- A. Charach, E. Yeung, T. Climans, and E. Lillie, (2011) "Childhood attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder and future substance use disorders: comparative meta-analyses," *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, vol. (50), 9–21,.
- Akanbi, M. I., Godwin, A., Anyio, B. T., Muhammad, M. & Ajiboye, S. A. (2015). Impact of substance abuse on academic performance among adolescent students of Colleges of Education in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, Vol 6(28), 108 – 112.
- Atoyebi, O. A. & Atoyebi, O. E. (2013). Pattern of substance abuse among senior secondary school students in a South western Nigerian City. *International Review of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4 (2) 54-65.
- Attah, A.P., Baba, E. and Audu, J.S. (2016), The Effects of Drug Abuse and Addiction on Academic Performance of Students in Federal Polytechnic Idah, Kogi State Nigeria, *International Journal of Democratic and Development Studies*, Vol. (2), (13-22)
- Ajibulu, E. (2011). Eradicating Drug Abuse in Nigeria- How feasible?. Retrieved May 24, 2012 from <http://www.modernghana.com/news/337520/1/eradicating-drug-abuse-in-nigeria-how-feasible.html>.
- Abdulahi, Z. (2009). "Drug abuse among youths: Strategies for school counselling", *The Nigerian Society of Educational Psychologists*, Jos: Nigeria. United Nations Organizations on Drug Council (UNODC) (2005). "World Health Organization Expert Committee on Dependence Producing Drugs. Fourteenth Report Urban Adolescents", *Child Development*, 61, 2032-2046.
- Adeyemo, F.O., Ohaeri, B., Pat, U. and Okpala, O. O. (2016). Prevalence of Drug Abuse Amongst University Students in Benin City, Nigeria: *Public Health Research*.
- Afuwai E.N. (2016). Drug Abuse on Socio-Emotional Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Kaduna State, Nigeria. Unpublished. American Psychiatric Association (2000). Diagnostic and Statistical manual of mental disorder. 4th ed, Washington D.C., United States of America.
- Barlow D.H. & Durand V.M. (2009) *Abnormal psychology: an integrative approach*. California: Wadsworth.
- Balogun, S.K. (2006). "Chronic intake of separate and combined alcohol and nicotine. Center for Disease Control, *Frequently asked questions on HIV/AIDS*. Retrieved from www.cdcnpin.org/hiv/faq/preventionJitm

- Chukwuka, C.O. (2015). *Truancy among Secondary School Students in Eboniyi South Education Zone*. Retrieved on 20th September, 2017 from <http://www.doublegist.com>
- Chaplin, T. M., & Sinha, R. (2013). Stress and parental addiction. In N. E. Suchman, M. Pajulo, & L. C. Mayes (Eds.), *Parenting and substance abuse: Developmental approaches to intervention* (pp. 3–23). NY: Oxford University Press.
- C. Kuhn, M. Johnson & A. Thomae (2010), “The emergence of gonadal hormone influences on dopaminergic function during puberty,” *Hormones and Behavior*, vol. (58), 122–137,
- “Child Welfare Information Gateway (2011), Definitions of Child Abuse and Neglect [Internet]. US Department of Health & Human Services,” <http://www.childwelfare.gov/pubs/factsheets/whatiscan.pdf>.
- Durani, Y. (2012). *Getting the facts: Drugs and alcohol*. Retrieved from <http://www.kidsheath.org/teens/drugsandalcohol.htm>. educational performance of some adolescents’ drug abusers in Ibadan”.
- Desalu, O. O., Iseh, K. R., Olokoba, A. B., Salawu, F. K., & Danburan, A. (2010). Smokeless Tobacco use in adult Nigerian population. *Journal of clinical practice*, 13(4), 382 – 387.
- Emmanuel, O.C, Valentine, T.P, Terna, M.F, Habu, H, Chia, T., Achukwu, C.E. (2017), Effects of Substance/Drug Abuse on the Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students in Mkar Metropolis, Gboko, Benue State *International Journal of Psychological and Brain Sciences*. Vol. (2) 40-45.
- E. M. Trucco, C. R. Colder, J. C. Bowker, & W. F. Wieczorek, (2011), “Interpersonal goals and susceptibility to peer influence: risk factors for intentions to initiate substance use during early adolescence,” *Journal of Early Adolescence*, vol. (31). 4, pp. 526– 547,
- FooYC, Tam C.L, Lee T.H. (2012), Family factors and peer influence in drug abuse: A study in rehabilitation centre. *International Journal of Collaborative Research on Internal Medicine & Public Health*.
- Hamisu Mamman Ahmad Tajuddin Othman (PhD) & Lim Hooi Lian (2014) Adolescent’s and Drugs Abuse in Nigeria *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare* Vol.4, No.(1)
- Giade, A. (2011,). How Nigeria’s Latest Drug Abuse Defies Legislat. *Daily Trust Newspaper*.
- Oshodi, O. Y., Aina, O. F., and Onajole, A. T. (2010). Substance use among secondary school students in an urban setting in Nigeria: prevalence and associated factors. *African journal of psychiatry*, 13(1), 52 – 57.
- Oluremi, D. F. (2012). Drug Abuse among Nigerian Adolescents strategies for counselling. *Journal of International Social Research*. 5(20):342-347.

- Hammond, D., Ahmed, R., Yang, W. S., Brukhalter, R., & Leatherdale, S. T. (2011). Illicit substance use among Canadian youth: Trends between 2002 and 2008. *Canadian Journal of Public Health*, Vol (102) 7–12.
- Leatherdale, S. T., & Ahmed, R. (2010). Alcohol, marijuana, and tobacco use among Canadian youth: Do we need more multi-substance prevention programming? *Journal of Primary Prevention*, Vol (31) 99–108.
- Razali, A., & Madon, Z. (2016). Issue and Challenges of Drug Addiction among Students in Malaysia. *Advances in Social Sciences Research Journal*, 3(8) 77-89.
- Mignon, S. Substance Abuse Treatment (2014). Options, Challenges, and Effectiveness; Springer: New York, NY, USA.
- H. K. Clark, C. L. Ringwalt, and S. R. Shamblen, (2011). “Predicting adolescent substance use: the effects of depressed mood and positive expectancies,” *Addictive Behaviors*, vol. (36) 488–493.
- O. D. Taylor, (2011). “Adolescent depression as a contributing factor to the development of substance use disorders,” *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, vol. (21) 696–710.
- M. R. Skeer, M. C. McCormick, S. L. T. Normand, M. J. Mimiaga, S. L. Buka, & S. E. Gilman, (2011) “Gender differences in the association between family conflict and adolescent substance use disorders,” *Journal of Adolescent Health*, vol. (49) 187–192.
- L. Tonmyr, T. Thornton, J. Draca, and C. Wekerle, (2010) “A review of childhood maltreatment and adolescent substance use relationship,” *Current Psychiatry Reviews*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 223–234.
- V. S. Singh, T. Thornton, & L. Tonmyr, (2011). “Determinants of substance abuse in a population of children and adolescents involved with the child welfare system,” *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, vol. (9) 382–397.
- B. F. Piko & M. A. Balazs, (2012) “Authoritative parenting style and adolescent smoking and drinking,” *Addictive Behaviors*, vol. (37) 353–356.
- T. C. Cheng and C. C. Lo, (2010). “The roles of parenting and child welfare services in alcohol use by adolescents,” *Children and Youth Services Review*, vol. (32) 38–43.
- S. Bava and S. F. Tapert, (2010) “Adolescent brain development and the risk for alcohol and other drug problems,” *Neuropsychology Review*, vol. (20) 398–413.
- Lee SI, Halimatul SAH. (2012.) *Students selling sex for dope*. Available at: <http://www.asiaone.com/News/Education/Story/A1Story20090906-165987.html>. Accessed July 17.
- National Abandoned Infants Assistance Resource Center (AIA). (2012). *Research to practice brief: Supporting children of parents with co-occurring mental illness and substance abuse*.

National Organization on Fetal Alcohol Syndrome. (2012). *FASD: What everyone should know*. Retrieved from <http://www.nofas.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/NOFAS-FASD-What-Everyone-Should-Know.pdf>

National Institute on Drug Abuse. (2011). *Prenatal exposure to drugs of abuse*. Retrieved from <http://www.drugabuse.gov/sites/default/files/prenatal.pdf>

Patrick, S. W., Schumacher, R. E., Benneyworth, B. D., Krans, E. E., McAllister, J. M., & Davis, M. M. (2012). Neonatal abstinence syndrome and associated health care expenditures: United States, 2000-2009. *Journal of the American Medical Association (JAMA)*, 307(18).

W. Y. Chen, J. Propp, E. deLara, and K. Corvo, (2011) "Child neglect and its association with subsequent Juvenile drug and alcohol offense," *Child and Adolescent Social Work Journal*, vol. (28) 273–290.